

Resource-efficient processes for the production and circularization of innovative RECYclable-by-DeSIGN fresh meat smart packaging from wood

[D. 7.2] Website and social media

PROJECT CO-FUNDED BY EUROPEAN COMMISSION

DISSEMINATION LEVEL		
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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ABBREVIATION	TERM
D&C	Dissemination and communication
WP	Work Packages
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
EU	European Union
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
CMS	Content Management System
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
HTML	HyperText Markup Language
FBP	Fibre-based packaging

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1. Executive Summary

The present document represents Deliverable 7.2 – REDYSIGN’s website. It has been developed as part of Work Package 7 – Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation.

The website is regarded as the primary digital point of contact and information for the REDYSIGN project, therefore it is considered as the main tool of the project’s Dissemination and Communication Plan [D 7.1] This document will serve to outline how the website is being developed to reflect the characteristics and innovative nature of the project. The design, management, maintenance, and content generation are crucial activities aligned with the main objective: addressing key target audiences, media, and stakeholders.

It is essential to reflect all the advances and results of the investigation in this project and to collect all the D&C actions. Additionally, it serves as a meeting place for partners and internal participants.

This report describes the overall website structure and design and defines the strategy that will be followed. It is organised into different parts: introduction, definition of the objectives of the website, description of the website technical characteristics, overall website structure and sections, how the website is going to be update, monitoring tools that will be used to measure website results and conclusions.

2. Introduction

The website aims to be the place where all the project official information will be gathered such as objectives, events and results. It is a meeting place for all stakeholders, the media and general public, and a way to facilitate external stakeholders' information about project activities.

The creation of REDYSIGN website started in month 1 of the project and has been launched in month 6. It has been carried out by Zabala Innovation with the support of Tecnalia as project coordinator to ensure accuracy and alignment with REDYSIGN's objectives. It operates under the domain www.redysign.eu and the general website language is English.

The website is designed under a clear and user-friendly structure, divided in the following sections:

1. **Home.** Initial screen with general information and the possibility to direct users into the different website sections.
2. **About.** Description of the project's motivation, general and specific objectives, and expected impacts.
3. **Innovation.** Definition of the four fields of development that the project will contribute to.
4. **Consortium.** List and description of all partners with the official link to their website and logo.
5. **News&Events.** News related to the project, and description of the organization of events within the framework of the project, and participation in other activities or events within the sector.
6. **Resources.** Downloadable materials (Communication Toolkit) from the project for media use or to promote the project at events. Press releases, publications or papers, and public deliverables will also be published.
7. **Contact.** Addressing and contact information.
8. **Footer:** Appropriate acknowledgement and reference to the funding by European Union's Horizon Europe Programme, contact, Privacy policy, cookie policy, terms and conditions in compliance with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), newsletter subscription box and social media widget.

3. Dissemination & Communication objectives

Aligned with the five objectives defined in the Dissemination and Communication plan [D 7.1], REDYSIGN website will serve to:

- **Attract the key target audiences and generate engagement with stakeholders:** Maintaining the audiences and stakeholders updated about the progress and news related to the project. Through the website, they will be able to access technical articles, research papers, public deliverables, pieces of news and sector policies, initiatives related to the European Commission, events created by this project or other projects with the same objective, workshops, etc.
- **Present key messages** in a visual and clear manner (see section: [1.1.2. Innovation](#)). The key messages of the project will be highlighted not only through content using key concepts and words but also through visual identity. This identity, reflecting the concepts of - material circularity and innovation, from fossil-based to wood-based materials, resource-efficiency processes driven by scientific and technological advancements, smart fibre-based packaging for fresh meat distribution as a substitute for current non-recyclable multi-plastic solutions, circularity and efficiency is evident in every visual aspect, including icons, typography, colours, pictures, and infographics.
- **Generate awareness** of the project: the website will consistently showcase the results and benefits of the biobased solutions to industry actors, public institutions, and society. The content of the website, which will be periodically updated, will be shared on social media and the newsletter, to attract visitors. Additionally, dissemination and communication strategies and campaigns developed online and offline will be complementary and will aim to attract visitors to the website.
- **Connect all communication channels** of the project. As the main information point, the website will display all project communication channels such as social media, newsletters, events, and workshops. Simultaneously, these channels will direct traffic to the website, fostering a continuous communication cycle.
- **Act as a reference point for other European projects** and showcase the project's collaboration with various European initiatives and bio-based policies. The website will serve as a platform to foster synergies by facilitating the exchange of links and incorporating mutual references on the partners' websites, Horizon Europe projects within the same field and other relevant agents in the sector. These synergies will be integral to the link-building strategy (see [4.3](#)).

4. Digital Marketing Strategy

REDYSIGN website is a central part of the digital marketing strategy deployed within the Dissemination and Communication Plan. The main pillars of the digital strategy regarding the website will be:

4.1. The use of Search Engine Optimization (SEO)

Search Engine Optimisation (SEO) involves the strategic process of optimizing a website to achieve a favourable ranking or positioning on search engines such as Google.

REDYSIGN website is SEO friendly and responds to the following standards:

- **Keyword Research and optimization:** Keyword research is essential to obtain optimal SEO results. Consequently, keywords related to the project will be analysed, improved, and updated for frequent usage. The proposed keywords for REDYSIGN are the following: REDYSIGN, biobased fresh meat packaging, Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking, Horizon Europe, European Project.
- **Content Organization:** The content is organized in a logical. This is not only good for SEO, but it also improves the user experience, making it more intuitive.
- **Content Promotion:** new content will be promoted by sharing it on social networks and building links to content (both internally and from external sites), to increase its visibility.

4.2. Inbound Marketing

SEO plays a crucial role in positioning our website effectively. That's the reason the marketing strategy is based on Inbound Marketing: attracting and engaging our key target audience through relevant and valuable content. This involves utilizing keywords, hyperlinks, and addressing the main questions of the project: What is the solution and contribution of REDYSIGN, the fields of development, how the process transforms wood into FBP, and the technologies applied.

The keywords will not only be present in the Home and main sections but also, we will incorporate relevant keywords naturally into the content, meta tags, and headers.

To create the content, we will use the Inverted Pyramid Method to structure content effectively. Provide the most critical information at the beginning to capture the audience's attention and answer their main questions promptly.

4.3. Link building

Once quality content is created, it is important to begin building backlinks to it. A backlink is a link back to our website from another page. It is an indicator of how important, or useful the content is for search engines so having a high number of quality backlinks is a big influential factor in ranking highly on search engines. According to Google, links are one of their top three ranking factors, which means there is a clear correlation between links and organic traffic. For this reason, the project will create synergies between REDYSIGN website and partners' websites, as well as with social media channels or other relevant initiatives of the sector or other Horizon Europe projects in the same field.

The website will also be actively promoted by all the partners on their own website homepages as well as on all their own communication channels such as social media profiles or newsletters. For example:

Figure 1. Link building partner's website

As for social media channels, they are essential to attract visitors. They will be used mainly to inform the audience about new updates (including the direct link) to assure that all public outputs of the project reach their online dissemination potential.

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5. Technical Characteristics

5.1. Full Responsive Content website

A fully responsive content website adjusts and adapts its layout and design to provide an optimal viewing and user experience across various devices, such as desktops, tablets, and mobile phones

The incorporation of state-of-the-art techniques in design also creates a quick and intuitive user experience while browsing the website. Some examples of how different parts of the website are seen on different devices can be found below:

Figure 2. Website view on the computer

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Figure 3. Website view on the phone

5.2. Built using WordPress CMS

WordPress is the most popular Content Management System (CMS) in the world. For this reason, it is probably the easiest and most powerful blogging and CMS in existence today. Some of its advantages and reasons for choosing it are the following:

- **Highly customizable:** WordPress allows to create and modify layouts and applications to meet all demands. This is especially useful for a 4-year project like REDYSIGN that could need to be updated in terms of design.
- **Design:** This option allows more freedom in designs as it can be customised, and visual effects can be added. WordPress allows for the creation and modification of layouts and applications.
- **Attractive for the users:** The resources in WordPress are easy reading, fact that invites website users to stay browsing for a longer time.
- **SEO friendly:** WordPress is known for having SEO built into the platform. This let's search engines get to know about the content, and get the website indexed and potentially moved up in the ranking.

5.3. Connection & data exchange protected under SSL Certificate

Secure Sockets Layer (SSL) is a security protocol; a standard security technology for establishing an encrypted link between a server and a client. It allows sensitive information (credit card numbers, social security numbers, and login credentials) to be transmitted securely. Normally, data sent between browsers

and web servers is sent in plain text—leaving you vulnerable to eavesdropping. To create a secure connection, an SSL certificate is installed on a web server and serves two functions:

- It authenticates the identity of the website.
- It encrypts the data that is being transmitted.

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6. Project website structure

The website structure presents the project in a continuous and non-linear manner, allowing users to scroll, and sections appear with the aim of being easy to navigate. The goal has been to illustrate in an attractive and original way the main pillars that support the project, using animated graphics and images.

It will contain the main information about the project (motivation, objectives, impacts and consortium), as well as the latest news and events related to the project. Moreover, it will also serve as a repository for public documents, REDYSIGN communication materials, publications, and press releases.

The project content and structure will be adjusted based on the evolving needs and desired outcomes throughout the project.

6.1. Menu

The website includes a responsive menu adapted to the responsive page design. Typography size increases when seeing it on computer screens to make it easier to read.

In the desktop version, the menu is located at both the top and bottom of the website. Additionally, when the user scrolls on the website, they can access the various sections listed in the main menu.

Figure 4. Website menu

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Regarding the mobile version, it has been designed as a floating menu so that it can be opened while scrolling by clicking the symbol in the top right side. The main function is to keep it visible so that users can continue browsing without having to go back to the top. The menu is also located at the bottom of the website so that if the user scrolls, they can quickly access the following sections. This makes navigation and reading simpler for the user.

Figure 5. Mobile menu

6.2. Home

The main objective of REDYSIGN homepage is to serve as a central point that effectively engages visitors in an illustrated manner and directs them to relevant sections of the site.

The homepage includes the following points:

- The page starts with a direct and clear message about the project, inviting the user to scroll and explore the project objective further.
- Main description of the project that redirects to "About".
- In the central section of the homepage, an image is incorporated to enhance the reading experience. As the project progresses, this will be substituted with the official project video to encourage users to stay on the website for an extended period, offering them comprehensive information about REDYSIGN.
- Description of the concept of the project that leads to "About". The informative content is complemented with an automatically animated graphic featuring two small windows that provide a summary of the project's concept. The first graphic addresses the current situation, and the second REDYSIGN explains the project's contributions to changing the existing scenario.
- The 4 fields of development on which the project will be developed are presented in animated card format with different images that make the website attractive and easy to understand. Furthermore, a quick slider is positioned to offer a snapshot view of the consortium that comprises the project and a summary of the latest news.
- Section to read a brief description about each of the partners.
- Latest news that redirects to the "News and events" page.
- Subscription box to the project's newsletter.

Figure 6. Structure of the website homepage

The homepage showcases the project logo in motion, with the 'e' rotating to create a dynamic visual identity that emphasizes the recycling concept of the project. This design is coordinated with the colour theme of the website. Two different shades of green, along with an off-white, have been used as the primary colours, complemented by wood-textured elements to add dynamism and enhance the attractiveness of the web.

All homepage content is connected with the rest of website pages to make it appealing for users to read it. Also, the newsletter subscription is situated at the end of the page and social media channels are facilitated to the users at the top and bottom of the page.

Each section includes contact details, addressing information, links to social media channels, references to funding from the Horizon Europe program, and a disclaimer that exempts the European Commission from responsibility.

Figure 7. Footer

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6.3. About

This section presents the project and its details in a more technical manner, primarily directed towards specialized stakeholders who may be interested in the details of the project organization. This menu section consists of three pages with content: About, Innovation, and Consortium.

Regarding the "About" page, it includes the key points of REDYSIGN. It is a comprehensive description of the project that addresses various aspects: motivation, main objectives of the project, and expected impacts. Additionally, data such as the number of partners, countries involved, budget, and duration are provided, along with a direct link to the Cordis page.

In the "Objective" section, various dropdowns are used with the purpose of providing specific information about the development of each one for those users interested in delving deeper into the topic.

Figure 8. About section

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1.1.1 INNOVATION

In this section, the 4 fields of development that the project will advance upon have been included. First, the current status of each line of work is described, followed by the project's contribution.

1. Efficient processes for transformation of wood into FBP.
2. Fresh food packaging from wood-derived products.
3. Technologies to enhance FBP recycling process.
4. Efficient recycling and upcycling technologies for contaminated FBP.

Figure 9. Innovation section

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1.1.2 PARTNERS

This section features the 13 partners that make up the REDYSIGN consortium. It includes a brief description of each of them, the logo, and a direct link to their official websites.

Figure 10. Consortium section

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6.4. News and events

The "News & Events" page is the main source of information about the progress and contributions of the REDYSIGN project, so it will be updated according to the project's need. News and interviews about the development and evolution of the project, achievement of milestones, and meetings will be published here.

Additionally, information about the organization of REDYSIGN's own events, attendance at events, and participation and presentation of the project at various industry forums, sector workshops, national and international conferences will be included, along with the event's own imagery. Partners will have the opportunity to contribute to the development of news or articles reflecting on the conclusions of activities in which they have participated. The goal is to provide unique value and highlight each partner's contributions.

Figure 11. News and events section

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6.5. Resources

This section contains downloadable materials for the project:

- **Communication toolkit** (REDYSIGN logos, Identity Guidelines). These materials will be used to maintain the project's visual consistency when presenting it at events, activities, workshops, or when disseminating information in other projects or publications. Additionally, corporate materials of the project (brochures, posters, etc.) will be uploaded. These materials are designed for use by communication or media departments. This streamlines the production of materials and enhances overall coverage.
- **Publications.** Open-access publications presenting or showcasing the project's results.
- **Press releases.** Project news archives for use and storage.
- **Public deliverables.** Technical documents of the project are available for public consultation.

Figure 12. Resources section

6.6. Contact

This website provides the email for contacting the REDYSIGN project through a form with GDPR consent. The email addresses of the Project Coordinator and the Communication Manager are also included for direct contact. This serves as a meeting point for stakeholders, other projects interested in networking or clustering, and the citizens to connect with the consortium.

Figure 13. Contact section

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7. Social Media Channels

This section describes the activated social media platforms (X and LinkedIn) of REDYSIGN, which have been created with the aim of sharing project updates and will be managed and updated by Zabala Innovation with the contribution of all consortium members. Content published by partners on their networks will also be shared to expand the project's impact and promote their contribution to the project.

Each month, content will be published on Twitter and LinkedIn following a strategic content calendar, encompassing diverse campaigns such as partners' contributions, objectives, impacts, and any other topics that might capture the interest of the project community. Posts will include creative elements showcasing the logo and brand backgrounds to enhance the visual image of the project. In addition, there will be links directing to the project website to increase visitor traffic.

7.1 X / Twitter

The official account is **@REDYSIGNProject**. www.twitter.com/REDYSIGNProject

Twitter is a dynamic and interactive platform that hosts a large community of the project's target audiences, including CBE JU-funded projects, EU institutions, media (specific magazines and international journals), influencers, and experts in the bio-based sector.

Given the characteristics of the social network, clear, concise, and direct messages will be posted two or three times a week with the purpose of building a community around the project. Consortium members and affiliated researchers will be tagged to enhance the project's impact on the network, and hashtags will be used to engage in conversations about the topic.

Figure 14. Twitter profile

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7.2 LinkedIn

LinkedIn account: REDYSIGN - www.linkedin.com/company/redysignproject/

LinkedIn serves as a dynamic hub for business professionals, entrepreneurs, and stakeholders across various sectors. It will be the primary network for establishing global connections and alliances with researchers from other international projects.

On LinkedIn, more in-depth posts will be included, targeting a scientific audience, as well as the business and industrial community. The technical information about the result will be combined with descriptive information about the project, each partner's contribution, or the development areas to make the project more accessible to a non-specialized audience. Additionally, it will be used as a platform to announce events organized during the project and invite various professionals through them.

Figure 15. LinkedIn profile

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7.3 YouTube

YouTube account: @REDYSIGNProject - www.youtube.com/@REDYSIGNProject

YouTube is a popular online video-sharing platform and the largest and most widely used video platform. Therefore, the presence of REDYSIGN on this platform is crucial for promoting the project.

Throughout the project, it will serve as a multimedia repository to host all project-related audiovisual resources. The YouTube channel is created with the mission of complementing, with multimedia content, the more informative information shared on X and LinkedIn. It will contain two specific videos about the project: one being the official video presentation of the project and its results, and the other featuring recordings of online seminars.

Figure 16. YouTube profile

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8. Roles and responsibilities

Zabala Innovation managed the domain purchase and hosting (www.redysign.eu) and also undertook the design and development of the website architecture and user experience. The graphic chart and web design adhere to REDYSIGN's visual identity guidelines. Zabala Innovation is responsible for consistently updating the project website in alignment with the project's evolution, needs, and progress, ensuring the reflection of key information about the project. This will be accomplished with the support of consortium members and their media representatives from the organization's communication or marketing departments.

To ensure content accuracy that reflects the project's progress, collaborative efforts are necessary in content creation, with all parties contributing their knowledge and latest advancements. To this end, partners will be requested each month to identify communication opportunities and provide information for creating articles on the website, covering milestones, achieved results, participation in events, press releases, and other relevant activities. If possible, each partner should also assist in supplying complementary materials (such as graphics, pictures from workshops and events, etc.) for subsequent use in communication activities.

The partners' collaboration is essential in the creation of news pieces for the project website. They are in direct contact with the project's progress and the ones most involved in the sector, aware of each news piece or publication that may affect them. For that reason, Zabala Innovation should encourage the partner's participation in the news creation process.

9. Results measurement

According to the Dissemination and Communication Plan, monitoring key indicators on the website and social media channels are essential to track the progress and keep the strategy updated.

The following KPIs have been established:

Website

The estimate is 50 visits per month. As a final objective, we aim for a total of 2K unique users for M48.

Social Media Channels

The community aims to reach 500 followers on Twitter and LinkedIn. These social media channels will help generate traffic to the website, nurturing user acquisition through the Organic Social channel.

Web analytics

To evaluate and measure website traffic and user behaviour, we will utilize the statistics obtained from Google Analytics 4 and the JetPack plugin integrated into the website.

Google Analytics 4 offers personalized views and graphs about the type of users, page views, average engagement time, and the most frequently visited pages accessible through the Google Analytics admin interface. Google Analytics 4 provides information about:

- How much traffic is coming to the site.
- Traffic resources. Analyses where your website traffic is coming from, whether through organic search, direct visits, referrals, or other channels.
- Visitors behaviour. What visitors are doing once they are on the site.

The report contains the following key data:

- **The total number of visitors**, including both new and returning visitors.
- **Percentage of new users**. The number and percentage of visitors who are new; the difference between the final percentage of visitors who are new and the 100% are the people who return.
- **Page views**. The total number of page views and those that receive more views.
- **Average interaction time**: Is the average time users spend interacting on the website.

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- **Bounce Rate:** The percentage of visitors who leave the site without viewing a second page. I.e., they click the 'back' button, type a new URL or close the window or session time-out.
- **Information about the visitors:** An overview of where in the world the visitors are located, the languages they speak, and the platforms they are using to look at the page.

In addition to the data obtained by Google Analytics 4, the **Jetpack** plugin will be used activated for statistics. Jetpack offers a wide range of features to enhance the functionality and performance of a WordPress website. This plugin will provide information about the website's performance, user interactions and traffic sources.

Social Media Analytics

For the measurement and evaluation of data on social networks, the proprietary measurement **tools** offered by Twitter and LinkedIn will also be employed. The combination of all these tools will allow a comprehensive view of the evolution of the project on social networks.

The data that can be obtained and will be measured are:

- **Twitter:** total number of impressions and engagement rate (link clicks, retweets and likes). The engagement rate is calculated by dividing the number of engagements (times users interacted with a Tweet) by the total impressions.
- **LinkedIn:** page views, unique visitors, reactions, feedback (comments) and times shared.

Reporting

The progression of indicators will be revised, and the main outcomes of the communication actions will be documented in D7.5 – 1st Report on Dissemination and Communication activities (M 12), D7.6 – 2nd Report on Dissemination and Communication activities (M 24), D7.8 – 3rd Report on Dissemination and Communication activities (M 36) and D7.10 – 4th Report on Dissemination and Communication activities (M 48), covering essential indicators outlined in the Dissemination and Communication plan:

- Number of visitors to the website per month.
- Number of followers in social media accounts.
- Number of newsletter subscribers.
- Information requests through the contact point.
- Engagement indicators.

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10. Conclusions

The website is a meeting point that must be kept alive. Zabala Innovation will oversee producing and publishing new content regularly, with the collaboration of the whole consortium.

Each partner should make use of their communication and networking channels and tools to reach the project community and spread news and results, and drive traffic to REDYSIGN website.

The website will be connected with social media channels, newsletters, and other initiatives. Using these platforms in combination will increase the digital project footprint and help maximise online awareness.

The website shown in this Deliverable (D7.2) is aligned with the D7.1 Dissemination & Communication Plan. It is an initial version, that will be periodically updated, completing the different sections with information coming from the corresponding WPs, refining the structure by considering specific requirements and functionalities, and creating new sections if needed. For this reason, although it will follow the main structures described throughout the document, new sections or changes can be introduced to ensure that it always reflects the advancements and responds to the needs of the D&C Plan and the project interests.